

Interface Location in Single Phase Stirred Tanks

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Abstract—In this work, study the location of interface in a stirred vessel with Rushton impeller by computational fluid dynamic was presented. To modeling rotating the impeller, sliding mesh (SM) technique was used and standard k-ε model was selected for turbulence closure. Mean tangential, radial and axial velocities and also turbulent kinetic energy (k) and turbulent dissipation rate (ε) in various points of tank was investigated. Results show sensitivity of system to location of interface and radius of 7 to 10cm for interface in the vessel with existence characteristics cause to increase the accuracy of simulation.

Keywords—CFD, Interface, Rushton impeller, Turbulence model.

I. INTRODUCTION

MIXING is one of the most common operations in chemical processes and knowledge of fluid flow pattern can considerably help to optimizing the operation. A large number of process applications involve mixing of single phase flow in mechanically stirred vessels. The optimum design and the efficiency of mixing operations are important parameters on product quality and production costs, so being aware of the different characteristics such as velocity distribution profiles and turbulence parameters in optimization of using the vessels is important. The flow motion in stirred tanks is 3-dimensional and complex and surrounding the impeller, the flow is highly turbulent. In recent years, computational fluid dynamic techniques increasingly used as a substitute for experiment to obtain the details flow field for a given set of fluid, impeller and tank geometries [1], [2]. In CFD, fully predictive simulations of the flow field and mixing time mainly use either the sliding mesh (SM) [3] or the multiple reference frame

(MRF) [4] approaches for account impeller revolution. The MRF approach predicts relative to the baffles [5] The SM approach is a fully transient approach, where the rotation of the impeller is explicitly taken in to account. The SM approach is more accurate but it is also much more time consuming than the MRF approach. SM simulation of a stirred tank content homogenization was first published by Jaworski and Dudczak [6]. They used the standard k-ε model and compared the results with the experimental data. Rushton turbine is the traditional six-blade disc turbine which has been widely used. The flat blade of the Rushton turbine leads to the formation of a pair of high-speed, low-pressure trailing vortices at the rear of each blade. [7], [8] Rushton impeller has been extensively studied as radial pumping impellers in both single phase [9], [10] and multi phase operations [11].

Fig. 1 Rushton impeller

II. METHODOLOGY

The CFD modeling involves the numerical solution of the conservation equations in the laminar and turbulent fluid flow regimes. Therefore, the theoretical predictions were obtained by simultaneous solution of the continuity and the Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations. The continuity and momentum equations for incompressible and Newtonian fluids:

$$\frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial t} + u_i \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} + \nu \frac{\partial^2 u_i}{\partial x_j^2} - \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_j} \quad (2)$$

$$\tau_{ij} = \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (3)$$

u_i is the velocity in the i th direction, ρ is the density, p is the pressure and ν is the kinematic viscosity of the fluid and τ_{ij} is stress tensor. For turbulent flow the above set of equations will

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have to be solved with Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS) to obtain the true variation of the velocity field. The governing equations are time-averaged Navier-Stokes equations and discretize and linearize the results with finite volume method.

A. CFD Method

Three-dimensional computational fluid dynamic (CFD) simulations was carried out in order to model the behavior of cylindrical stirred vessels with concave impeller and Rushton turbine for baffled configurations. Commercial CFD code, Fluent version 6.3, was used for solving a set of nonlinear equations formed by discretization of the continuity, the tracer mass balance and momentum equations. A computational grid consisting of two parts: an inner rotating cylindrical volume enclosing the turbine, and an outer, stationary volume containing the rest of the tank. The structured grids, composed of non-uniformly distributed hexahedral cells, were used in the two parts. The grid used in the impeller region was dandified to get a more accurate description of the impeller. The total grid nodes numbers are 600000 in the tank. In this study, the MRF solution was used as a starting point. The simulation was then switched to unsteady SM model and first order upwind scheme for discretization also the SIMPLE algorithm for pressure velocity coupling was used. Water at 25°C was used as the test fluid ($\mu=10^{-3}$ Pa.s, $\rho=998.2$ kgm⁻³). Dimensions of the stirred tank and details of Rushton impeller are shown in Table I. Fig. 2 shows inner volume of Rushton impeller with hexahedral mesh for clockwise rotating.

Fig. 2 Inner volume of Rushton impeller with hexahedral mesh for clockwise rotating

TABLE I DIMENSIONS OF STIRRED TANK AND RUSHTON BLADE	
Impeller	Dimension
Tank diameter(m)	0.3
Impeller diameter(m)	0.1
Disk diameter(m)	0.66
Disk thickness (m)	0.0035
Blade height (m)	0.25
Blade length (m)	0.25
Blade thickness (m)	0.002
Blade angle(degree)	45
Bottem clearance(m)	0.01

For investigate the location of interface in Rushton impeller, cylindrical has been used with 6.5cm height and variable radius which surrounded symmetrical the blades. Values of

cylinder radius have been adjusted on 5.75, 7.5, 9, 10.5 and 11.75. These radiuses cover respectively the closest distance to the impeller till closest distance to the baffle.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In Figs. 3 to 14 simulation results for comparing with experimental data have been presented with laboratory work of Wu and Patterson [12] in r/R of 0.38, 0.5, 0.6 and 0.7 that R is tank radius and r is radial distance from the blade. Radial, angular and axial velocity profiles have been provided in the form of normalized by tip speed of impeller in terms of $2Z/W$ that Z is axial distance from impeller disk and W is blade height of Rushton impeller. The impeller rotation speed is considered 300rpm. Time step is 0.001sec and to control of reaching quasi-steady state drawing the figures of kinetic energy integral is used. Radial velocity variations at different distances of interface have been presented in Figs. 3 to 6.

Fig. 3 Normalized mean radial velocity for different distances of interface in $r/R=0.38$

Fig. 4 Normalized mean radial velocity for different distances of interface in $r/R=0.5$

Fig. 5 Normalized mean radial velocity for different distances of interface in $r/R=0.6$

Fig. 7 Normalized mean tangential velocity for different distances of interface in $r/R=0.38$

Fig. 6 Normalized mean radial velocity for different distances of interface in $r/R=0.7$

Fig. 8 Normalized mean tangential velocity for different distances of interface in $r/R=0.5$

According to the figs can be seen the curves obtained using different interfaces have been able to predict the radial velocity curves. With radial movement from impeller toward the tank wall speed decreases gradually and figs are flatter. In case of locating interface in the farthest and nearest distance from the impeller (radiuses 5.75 and 11.75 cm) simulation results comparing to experimental results have higher values of errors but other cases, to determination of radial velocity have been shown less than errors among which 5.75 and 9cm radiuses are more consistent with experimental results.

In Figs. 7 to 10 axial variations of tangential velocity are presented. All states except near the blade and close to the tank wall have been able to predict the shape of the tangential velocity.

The results of the interfaces between the radius of 7.5 to 9 cm show better performance. Radius 10.5cm after the second and third models has less error.

Fig. 9 Normalized mean tangential velocity for different distances of interface in $r/R=0.6$

Fig. 10 Normalized mean tangential velocity for different distances of interface in $r/R=0.7$

Fig. 13 Normalized mean axial velocity for different distances of interface in $r/R=0.6$

Figs. 11 to 14 are shown the axial velocity in different radiuses. Maximum axial velocity is observed in the area that fluid drawn to inside impeller flow. According to the figures, it is seen that interfaces in 5.75 and 11.75cm have maximum errors in axial velocity distribution. Also interface in radius of 10.5cm although has less error than the first and fifth models, but has more errors than the second and third models. So the second and third models have the best performances that with increasing ratio of r/R are almost show the same errors.

Fig. 11 Normalized mean axial velocity for different distances of interface in $r/R=0.38$

Fig. 14 Normalized mean axial velocity for different distances of interface in $r/R=0.7$

Fig. 12 Normalized mean axial velocity for different distances of interface in $r/R=0.5$

Velocity data for turbulent kinetic energy (K) with square of tip speed $V^2_{tip} = (\Pi ND)^2$ and for turbulent kinetic energy dissipation rate (ϵ) with N3D2 have been normalized that N is impeller rotation speed, D is impeller diameter and H is tank height. According to Figs. 15 to 18 of turbulent kinetic energy and turbulent kinetic energy dissipation rate, it is observed that the interface between the near and far from blade shape of the curves in figures has been removed from general case.

Fig. 15 Normalized turbulent kinetic energy for different distances of interface in $r/R=0.38$

Fig. 16 Normalized turbulent kinetic energy for different distances of interface in $r/R=0.6$

Fig. 17 Normalized turbulent energy dissipation rate for different distances of interface in $r/R=0.38$

Fig. 18 Normalized turbulent energy dissipation rate for different distances of interface in $r/R=0.6$

The presented results show that most of the models were able to predict the general pattern of the Rushton impeller and in all models jet-like flow pattern with increasing distance from the tip of the blade is reduced, which is consistent with experimental results. Also value of error in very near radiuses to impeller is increased.

IV. CONCLUSION

A CFD model is developed to study the location of interface in baffled stirred vessel with Rushton impeller and results compared with experimental data. Senility of the subject to get results with the highest accuracy and the least error cause to investigating the axial, radial and tangential velocities, turbulent kinetic energy and turbulent energy dissipation rate in different points of the tank. As it shown most of the cases can predict the pattern of Rushton impeller but for nearest and farthest distances from the impeller results are very weak. So according to the simulation and experimental results, the best location of interface for Rushton impeller in a tank with 0.3m diameter is a cylindrical with radius of 7 to 10cm.

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